

PROFILING THE DRIVERS OF MARKET POWER OF WINERIES. THE CASE OF SOUTHERN BULGARIA

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Abstract

During last decade the competition on wine market of Europe is going higher. This is a result from regulation of wine industry under common agricultural policy of European Union. In such market condition the leading role of all departments in every winery is marketing unit. The purpose of this research is to be estimated the influence of scale of equity and strategic marketing activities on market power of winery. Using statistical approach is verifying the basic thesis concerning the basic factors which define the market power in wine sector. The statistical analysis is developed in two stages - 1) influence the scale of equity and assets on market share and 2) influence of strategic marketing activates on market share. It can be concluded that the studied factors affecting the market power of wine enterprises. The great variety of the offered product range on the market shows that wine enterprises pursue an active product policy. The other elements of the marketing mix are not so important.

Keywords: market power, concentration of capital, marketing activities, market share, equity, assets wine enterprises

Abstrakt

Während des letzten Jahrzehnts wird der Wettbewerb auf dem europäischen Weinmarkt immer stärker. Dies ist ein Ergebnis der Regulierung der Weinindustrie im Rahmen der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik der Europäischen Union. In solchen Marktbedingungen ist die führende Rolle aller Abteilungen in jeder Weinkellerei die Vermarktungseinheit. Der Zweck dieser Forschung ist es, den Einfluss des Umfangs der Equity und der strategischen Marketingaktivitäten auf die Marktmacht der Weinkellerei zu bewerten. Mit Hilfe des statistischen Ansatzes wird die Grundthese über die grundlegenden Faktoren, die die Marktmacht im Weinsektor definieren, überprüft. Die statistische Analyse wird in zwei Etappen entwickelt - 1) Einfluss des Umfangs von Eigenkapital und Aktiva auf den Marktanteil und 2) Einfluss der strategischen Marketingaktivitäten auf den Marktanteil. Es kann geschlossen werden, dass die untersuchten Faktoren die Marktmacht der Weinunternehmen beeinflussen. Die große Vielfalt der angebotenen Produktpalette auf dem Markt zeigt, dass die Weinunternehmen eine aktive Produktpolitik verfolgen. Die anderen Elemente des Marketing-Mixes sind nicht so wichtig.

Stichworte: Marktmacht, Kapitalkonzentration, Marketingaktivitäten, Marktanteil, Eigenkapital, Aktiva Weinunternehmen

Résumé

Au cours de la dernière décennie, la concurrence sur le marché du vin en Europe s'est accrue. Ceci est le résultat de la réglementation de l'industrie du vin dans le cadre de la politique agricole commune de l'Union européenne. Dans ces conditions de marché, le rôle principal de tous les départements de chaque cave est l'unité de commercialisation. L'objectif de cette recherche est d'estimer l'influence de l'échelle des capitaux propres et des activités de marketing stratégique sur le pouvoir de marché des caves. L'utilisation de l'approche statistique permet de vérifier la thèse de base concernant les facteurs fondamentaux qui définissent le pouvoir de marché dans le secteur viticole. L'analyse statistique est développée en deux étapes - 1) l'influence de l'échelle des capitaux propres et des actifs sur la part de marché et 2) l'influence des activités de marketing stratégique sur la part de marché. On peut conclure que les facteurs étudiés affectant le pouvoir de marché des entreprises du secteur vitivinicole. La grande variété de la gamme de produits proposés sur le marché montre que les entreprises vitivinicoles mènent une politique de produit active. Les autres éléments du marketing mix ne sont pas aussi importants.

Mots clés: pouvoir de marché, concentration de capital, activités de marketing, part de marché, capitaux propres, actifs entreprises viticoles

Introduction

In recent years the European wine market is determined by strong competition due to accumulated surpluses resulting from the impact of agricultural policy in the sector. This determines the leading unit in each wine company is marketing department. The increase in market power requires diversity in the enterprise, which complicate its management. This begs the question what is the impact of company size on market power and efficiency. According to research of (Lipsey, 1987); (Kirpalani, 1987); (Armstrong, Collopy, 1996); (Bloodgood, Katz, 2004), (Borisov and Marinov, 2013) there is a direct correlation between the amount of capital invested in the enterprise and its market power. Key factors for the increase in market power that management can use are: (1) cost leadership and (2) product differentiation. Larger enterprises have the opportunity to accumulate substantial financial capital through the issuance and sale of shares, which is a prerequisite for building large-sized production facilities, enabling the realization of economies of scale, and hence the price leadership (Borisov, Radev and Dimitrova, 2014). These businesses have clearly developed organizational and management structure, which identifies and marketing departments are saturated with capital defining higher fixed costs that make them inert and less adaptable to changes in market demand. Enterprises that do not have large financial capital achieve higher market power relying on product differentiation. These organizations do not concentrate significant capital, which gives them the advantage of being more adaptable to market demands than the big ones in the industry.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and assess the impact of the size of capital and executing strategic marketing activities on the market power of wine enterprises in southern Bulgaria in the production and marketing of wine.

We define a system of indicators by which to analyze and assess the market power of the wine cellars. This system includes two groups of indicators - drivers and performance indicators:

- *Drivers* - determine the potential of the wine company to increase its market power in the industry. As such are determined: total assets, the amount of equity available to marketing departments and viability of strategic marketing activities.
- *Performance indicators* - they are those that determine the achieved degree of market power in the wine business. They are also used as a tool for comparative analysis of different size and organization of wine businesses. As such, the most often used is the market share (Pride, McKee, 1989). The market share of surveyed enterprises is calculated based on sales of wine in the domestic market.

Through statistical hypothesis testing we prove or reject the basic hypothesis explaining the dependence of the factors of market power. The conceptual argument to be checked for authenticity is that the concentration of capital in the wine company and execution of strategic marketing activities determine the market power in the industry. The analysis of the accuracy of the conceptual hypothesis proceeds in two successive stages:

Stage (1) Assessing the impact of the degree of concentration of capital in the wine company on its market power. For making this evaluation we use the following indicators - assets and size of equity. (Bloodgood, Katz, 2004).

Verifying the accuracy of the conceptual view is carried out using the statistical method - a simple correlation between the two factors.

The following statistical hypotheses are raised for verification:

H⁰¹ - there is no statistically significant correlation between the driver "assets" and the performance indicator "market share";

H¹¹ - there is statistically significant correlation between the driver "assets" and performance indicator "market share";

H⁰² - there is no statistically significant correlation between the driver "amount of equity" and the performance indicator "market share";

H¹² - there is statistically significant correlation between the driver "amount of equity" and the performance indicator "market share".

Stage (2) Evaluation of the impact of strategic marketing activities on the market power of the wine company. The main activities are presented in Table. 1. In conducting the analysis, strategic marketing activities are defined as drivers and achieved market share as performance indicator. The correlation between drivers and performance indicators are tested by applying the χ^2 -analysis.

For the purposes of the the analysis we use data from official accounting records of wineries (for the period 2018-2019) - balance sheet, plan income and expenditure plan, statement of cash flows and conducted own survey performed on marketing activities. There were examined 55 wine enterprises in southern Bulgaria. Data processing and analyzing the correlation between factors of market power are performed with SPSS software and MS Excel.

Table 1. Strategic marketing activities. Source: own interpretation

Strategic marketing activities
Clear definition of mission of organization
Sharing the mission between employees in organization
Segmentation of market
Development of target groups
Development of marketing mix for every single target group
Establishment of marketing information system
Execution of audit of external business conditions
Defining marketing goals in written form
Commitment of market goals with output of strategic audit
Clearly defined marketing strategy
Using competitive advantage as basic tool for development of marketing strategy
Coordination of marketing strategy with other functional strategies of organization
Financial cover of marketing strategy
Clearly distributed responsibilities between employees on execution of marketing strategy
Development of control system

Results

Corellation between the degree of concentration of capital and achieved market power. The characteristic of the studied group of objects shows that the majority of wine companies are joint-stock companies - 58% of total entities. The next preferred legal form is the sole limited liability company - 20% of the surveyed enterprises in the sector. At least many are wine businesses that are sole joint stock companies - 4% of total surveyed companies. The structure of the sample showed that the preferred form of raising capital in the industry is a joint stock company.

Figure 1. Distribution of wineries according to their assets. Source: own survey, 2018-2019

There is a domination of small wine companies with assets up to 20 million BGN - 80% of the surveyed entities. Next major group is the medium-sized enterprises (13%) who own assets up to 40

million BGN. Only 7% of the surveyed enterprises are defined as large, with assets over 40 million BGN. The results from survey show that 4% of all wine enterprises possess 32% of the assets in the industry. These businesses entities holds together - 64% fo the market. This tendency sets a strong concentration of capital in few wine companies that serve a significant share of the domestic wine market.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of surveyed wineries

Statistic indicator	Assets 000 BGN	Equity 000 BGN
Min	5	3
Max	169 750	64283
Range	169 745	64,280
Sum	904 521	316 854
Mean	16445.8	5760.98
Standart deviation	30138.2	12450.35
Coefficient of variation - %	183	216

The total assets of the surveyed wine companies are 904.5 million BGN and average amount of assets per company is 16 million BGN. The coefficient of variation (183%) showed that the study group of enterprise is heterogeneous. The average amount of equity per wine enterprise is 5.8 million BGN. The wine sector varies widely depending on the amount of equity that have invested in single business entity, respectively coefficient of variation is 216%. The higher average value of the indicator – “the amount of equity” comparer to the indicator – “total assets” shows that overall wine enterprises acquire its assets using mostly equity.

On Figures 2 and 3 is given the correlation among the drivers and performance indicators of surveyed wine companies

Figure 2. Graphic interception between assets and market share

Figure 3. Graphic interception between equity and market share

It was found that there is a very high degree of correlation between the driver “assets” and performing indicator “market share”. The coefficient of determination is 0.91, while the correlation 0.95. This proves that the amount of assets is a factor that strongly influences and determines the size of the market share of wine companies in the sector.

Equity now also systematically influence the formation of market share. The coefficient of determination in this dependence was 0.74. The correlation coefficient indicates greater dependence between the studied factors, respectively value is 0.86.

Both studied factors have rights relating to market share. With the increase in assets and the amount of equity ceteris paribus increases market share studied wine businesses. According to the value of beta regression coefficient (B1) climate resultant value market share caused by the change in size of assets and equity in the industry is as follows:

- an increase in assets 1 000 BGN is achieved change in the market share of 0.95%;
- to increase the amount of equity in 1000 BGN is achieved the market share of 0.84%.

Table 3. Results of statistical analysis of basic factors which define market share

Factors which are drivers	Assets	Equity
Multiple R	0.9524	0.8593
R square	0.9071	0.7386
Adjusted R Square	0.9054	0.7336
Degree of relevance	very strong	strong
Type of relevance	positive	positive
Regression coefficient b0	-0.02824729	0.553235
Regression coefficient b1	0.000112273	0.000241
Beta coefficient B1	0.952442307	0.842932134

Influence of strategic marketing activities on the market power. Wine companies are grouped into three groups (with decreased market share, with constant market share, with an increased market share). In the period it found that 22 enterprises have increased their market share in other 16 there is no change, and 17 enterprises decreased their market share.

Through the resulting frequency of distributions, using χ^2 -analysis to reveal those activities which have not accidental (objective) correlation with performance indicator "market share". The results of χ^2 -analysis are presented in Table 3. The significance level of alpha-value is $\alpha = 0,05$.

Based on the results of the statistical analysis found that the implementation of strategic marketing activities with the exception of one of them (a clearly defined mission) results on the company's market share. The analysis confirms the research thesis that strategic marketing activities are a significant factor in the management of market share.

Table 4. Statistical clusters according to achieved market share and accomplishment of marketing activities

Strategic marketing activities	Market share	Kramer's coefficient
Does the company have a marketing information system?	there is relevance	0.5465
Does the company do an external audit?	there is relevance	0.5465
Does the company clearly define the mission?	there is no relevance	–
Are your employees are familiar with the mission and give it support?	there is relevance	0.2098
Does the company make segmentation of the market?	there is relevance	0.6875
Do you know the specific features of every target group?	there is relevance	0.6072
Do you do a specific marketing mix for every target group?	there is relevance	0.6072
Do you have in written form the marketing goals?	there is relevance	0.4015
Does your company develop a strategic plan in written form?	there is relevance	0.1827
Does your company have defined marketing strategy for achievement of market goals?	there is relevance	0.4315
Does your company use competitive advantage as a basic tool for development of marketing strategy?	there is relevance	0.4233
Does your company coordinate the marketing strategy with other functional strategies?	there is relevance	0.4233
Does your company manage financial recourses for execution of marketing strategy?	there is relevance	0.4233
Is it clear all responsibilities of every one in the company according execution of marketing strategy?	there is relevance	0.3645
Does your company have a control system which monitors the execution of marketing strategy?	there is relevance	0.6724

The strength of established statistical dependencies measured by the coefficient of Kramer. The results show that only part of the strategic marketing activities (6 of them, see table 4) have sufficient relevance to the market share. Strength of the relationship is significant ($V^2 > 0,5$). These marketing activities are: (1) The building control system of marketing strategy; (2) Analysis of the external

environment; (3) Market segmentation; (4) Developing a profile of the segment; (5) Development of specific marketing mix for each target segment; (6) The existence of a system for monitoring the implementation of marketing strategy.

Conclusions

It can be concluded that the studied drivers are strongly affecting the market power of wine enterprises. The great variety of the offered product range on the market shows that wine enterprises pursue an active product policy. The other elements of the marketing mix of wine company are not so important. The forecast is that in the future the wineries have to maintain market positions in industry will increasingly rely on the implementation of strategic marketing activities. For this purpose, all elements of the marketing mix will be important to be developed. This will require the allocation of more financial funds.

Based on statistical analysis we can make the following conclusions to achieve greater efficiency in wine sector:

- The sector distributed corporate organizational forms, allowing for wider attracting financial capital and full implementation of marketing activities. The structure of enterprises in business-legal form is explained by the significant investment required to enter the sector;
- There is a strong dual structure of the industry in terms of size of assets and market share.
- The amount of assets defines the market power of wine companies, taking into account investments to improve the condition of the technological equipment and buildings. As a result, enterprises successfully meet the requirements of the market. There is steady increase of sensitivity to the quality of products among wineries, and also sharpened competition in recent years;
- Although companies use different forms of financing equity occupies a leading position which gives a high degree of financial independence. And at the same time is an important factor for the growth of their market power;

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